

Current Needs of Making Changes in Transportation and Energy Policies to Mitigate the Bad and Harmful Impacts of Environmental Pollution; An Indian Perspective

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Abstract

Climate change mitigation is about reducing the release of greenhouse gas emissions that heat our world. Mitigation strategies consist of retrofitting buildings to make them more energy efficient; receiving renewable energy sources such as solar, wind and small hydropower; helping cities create more feasible transportation such as rapid transportation, electric vehicles and biofuels; and advancing more economical land and forest uses. Mitigation measures are all such functioning that are undertaken to scale back and control greenhouse emission outflows, while adaptation measures are supported reducing vulnerability to global climate change impacts. Practice Energy efficiency, more prominent use of renewable energy, Electrification of industrial processes, Effective means of transportation use: electric public transport, bicycle, carbon charge, etc. In the transport division, India is heavily dependent on

fossil fuels. This has led to challenges with air pollution, energy security and greenhouse gas emissions, which are likely to increase with increasing demand for transport and energy. Petrol and diesel make up more than 90 percent of India's transport sector's last energy use. Transport is India's fastest-growing energy-consuming sector with a growth rate of 6.8 percent, about 90 percent of which is due to road transport. Seven of the top 10 polluted cities in the world are in India, according to the World Air Quality Report 2018. For example, in Delhi, it has been found that vehicle emissions are the major contributor to rising air pollution compared to other sources such as manufacturing, households, thermal power plants, and agricultural sources. In India alone in 2018, air pollution was estimated to have caused 1.25 million deaths; i.e., 12.5% of total deaths. Electric vehicles are capable of reducing toxic air pollution compared to traditional vehicles and, most significantly, removing emissions from cities with safety and livability benefits. As India moves away from polluting coal-based electricity, the benefits of EVs will move forward. Shifting taxes on fuel and subsidies for renewable energy will greatly benefit air pollution: reduced prices for the use of petrol and diesel, cuts in air pollution from the coal-fired period, and going forward with India's Electric Vehicles environmental accreditation.

Key Words –Greenhouse gas, Energy efficiency, Fossil fuels, Air pollution, Electric Vehicles, Biofuels.

Introduction:

Environmental pollution is a big risk to health, with India reported having some of the world's highest rates. In India, air pollution exposure and its impact in every state of India on deaths, disease burden, and life expectancy. India's air pollution has a discordantly strong death and infection load. In North India's low socio-demographic index states, this burden is

generally the highest.

Reducing the sufficient avoidable death and disease burden from this major environmental threat depends on the rapid deployment of active multisectoral policies across India that are homologous with each state's severity of air pollution. Environmental pollution contributes significantly to the international risk of premature death and disease. India has one of the world's highest levels of exposure to air pollution.

In India, transport vehicles, ground dust, residential and commercial wood burning, waste burning, farm stubble burning, diesel generators, and coal burning are the major components of air pollution of thermal power generation, factory emissions, etc. Ground-level atmosphere ozone is created by responding in the presence of sunlight with nitrogen oxides and volatile organic compounds released by automobiles, power plants, factories, and other sources. Rapidly developing countries like India are facing the dual challenge of both environmental and domestic air pollution exposures.

Many cars operate on fossil fuels, and as demand for oil continues to rise, it presents a significant pollution challenge. Developments in advanced fuel and electric vehicle technology

will improve the automobile sector's energy efficiency and environmental impact and will play a key role in reducing environmental pollution's ill effects in India. In environmentally sustainable transport, the function of alternative fuels such as energy, fuel cells, as well as advanced additives and biofuels, oils will ultimately improve the quality of our environmental air.

India is unveiling the 2013 'National Electric Mobility Mission Plan (NEMMP) 2020' to document national energy security issues, vehicle emissions, and domestic production capacity expansion. Recapitulating its contribution to the Paris Agreement, India's government has a goal of making a significant shift to electric vehicles by 2030. Energy Efficiency Services Limited (EESL), Ministry of Power's joint venture with PSU, Govt. The procurement and sale of electric vehicles in India are of particular importance to India.

Methods:

The indicator of susceptibility to emissions from airborne particulate matter was the mean amount of PM_{2.5} in the atmosphere per year. The measurements of Indian subjection of airborne particulate matter 2.5 are based on multiple satellite-based information coupled with ground-level transport of atmospheric particulate matter 2.5 data.

The major sources of information for solid fuel use in India included national health surveys such as the Public Family Health Survey and the District Level Household Survey, National Sample Survey Organization national surveys, and the Indian Census, as well as many other published and undisclosed epidemiological studies.

Results and Discussions:

As for the aerodynamic size of particles, the smaller particles are understood from medical literature, the better they can penetrate the natural barriers in the human body and eventually reach the bloodstream. The potential hazard of the smallest molecules is their composition, as all cells are potential targets for inflammation and damage to cell structures through the bloodstream. The most common way in which particles reach the human body is through inhalation and skin contact exposure. Because exposure to poor air quality is practically constant in urbanized regions with dense traffic, it contributes significantly to an increased risk of inhabitants premature death.

In order to make progress on solutions to resolve and address these problems, corporate and government must go hand in hand and implement concrete plans to monitor these bad environmental pollution impacts. The country's Oil Marketing Companies (OMCs) would procure biodiesel from the UCO. The mandate given to the Union Ministry of India to reduce oil product dependency by 2022 can be achieved by improving production, improving energy efficiency, promoting conservation and promoting alternative fuels. Such as: promoting ethanol, 2-G ethanol, compressed biogas, and bio-diesel.

According to the ministry of the Union of India, the ethanol mixture of petrol has already risen to 8% and would soon reach 10%. The government plans to allow ethanol production from surplus food grains. Distribution network set up in over 400 districts and 300 letters of intent has already been signed with businessmen to set up compressed biogas plants. Within the nation, there is a range of techniques that can be used to turn waste into useful products.

Is electric driving really the environment's best solution?

The answer is yes, the short answer.

Electric vehicles emit twice as much carbon dioxide (CO₂) as diesel engines in a full life cycle. When vehicles are running on green energy, more than 10 times could reduce carbon dioxide emissions.

Parker built the first electric vehicle in 1884. The first vehicle that reached the 100 km / h speed limit was Jenatzy's 1899 electric "la Jamais Contente." In the early twentieth century, however, the petrol engine car took over the market. A renewed interest by electric vehicles has been observed due to the oil crisis of the 1970s.

Can everyone in the Near Future drive Electric Vehicles?

We're at a turning point, however. The driving force of the market is not just the diesel gate. By offering models that go well beyond the small city car, Tesla has opened the market. Electric cars are now interested in a whole new type of consumer. Both manufacturers work on electrical designs. Things are moving, therefore. It also depends on policymakers and the incentives offered by these firms and the government.

Conclusions:

A reduction in air pollution is one of the benefits of reducing fossil fuel consumption. On average, a rise of 10 micrograms per cubic meter of air pollution pollutants reduces the life expectancy for patients by about 9-11 years. Tiny particles are unleashed when we burn fossil fuels, causing air pollution. This is known to cause premature death and strategies aimed at reducing our fossil fuel consumption often

specify the likely health benefits – and cost savings associated with reducing air pollution. In order to develop better-sophisticated policies and reduce the use of fossil fuel, we need to understand the real impact of long-term air pollution subjection.

The government has emphasized the achievement of the country's energy reliability, security, and reliability with the goal of reducing import subordination and dependence, i.e. the use of fossil fuels by 10 percent by 2022. To achieve this goal, acquire a five-pronged plan that includes, Growing Domestic Production, Following Biofuels & Renewable, Energy Efficiency Standards, Development and Trade-off Upgrade in Refinery Processes and Demand. This provides for a planned role for biofuels in the basket of Indian Energy.

That debate of import dependency for fuel needs in conjunction with environmental pollution concerns has guided and navigates the need for biofuels that have superior environmental benefits and are compatible with fossil fuel economically. National Biofuels Policy-2018 sets the new agenda in an orderly manner with the redefined position of materializing renewable business innovations. Its strategy aims to bring renewed focus into the context of global developments and the national scenario.

In 2013, India launched the 'National Electric Mobility Mission Project (NEMMP) 2020' to resolve national energy security issues, vehicle emissions, and domestic production capacity expansion. The Government of India,

reiterating its contribution to the Paris Agreement, aimed at making a major move towards electric vehicles by 2030. To order to produce convincing evidence that allows countries to reduce their use of fossil fuels, India will concentrate on a strong and steady way of determining the economic benefit of reducing air pollution.

References:

Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB), Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, Government of India **Air quality monitoring, emission inventory and source apportionment study for Indian cities—national summary report**, CPCB, New Delhi (2011)

SK Guttikunda, R Goel, P Pant **Nature of air pollution, emission sources, and management in the Indian cities**, Atmos Environ, 95 (2014), pp. 501-510

Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Kanpur, Delhi Pollution Control Committee, Department of Environment **Comprehensive study on air pollution and greenhouse gases (GHGs) in Delhi**

IIT Kanpur, Delhi Pollution Control Committee and Department of Environment, **National Capital Territory Delhi** (2016)

Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas, Government of India **Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana**

Press Information Bureau, Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, Government of India. Government has made serious efforts to deal with air pollution: **Environment Ministry**. pib.nic.in (Sept 14, 2018).

Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, Government of India **National clean air programme—India**, 14th Sep 2018

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development and Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, OECD-FAO

Agricultural Outlook 2011–2020. Ch. 3 (Rome: FAO, 2011). Rana B.S., Kumar R., Tiwari R., Kumar R., Joshi R.K., Garg M.O., Sinha A.K., 2013. Transportation fuels from co-processing of waste vegetable oil and gas oil mixtures. Biomass Bioenergy. 56, 43-52.

Rahman K.M.; Fahimi B.; Suresh G.; Rajarathnam A.V.; Ehsani M., “Advantages of switched reluctance motor applications to EV and HEV: design and control issues”, **IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications**, Vol. 36, Issue 1, Jan.-Feb. 2000, pp. 111 – 121.

Messagie M.; Boureima F.-S.; Coosemans T.; Macharis C.; Van Mierlo V. A Range-Based Vehicle Life Cycle Assessment Incorporating Variability in the Environmental Assessment of Different Vehicle Technologies and Fuels. *Energies* 2014, 7, 1467–1482.

Hooftman N.; Oliveira L.; Messagie M.; Coosemans T.; Van Mierlo J. Environmental Analysis of Petrol, Diesel and Electric Passenger Cars in a Belgian Urban Setting. *Energies* 2016, 9, 84

PRIYA PARSOYA, RAKSHIT AMETA and SURESH C. AMETA, Zinc Ferrite: An efficient Photo catalyst for Degradation of Rose Bengal, *Int. J. Chem. Sci.*, 44, 3256-3264 (2016).

PRIYA PARSOYA and SURESH C. AMETA, Use of Zinc Ferrite as Efficient Photo catalyst for Degradation of Toludine Blue J. *Curr. Chem. Pharm. Sci.*:6(4),63-69 (2016).

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